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UKRAINE AND INTEROPERABILITY AS LONG-TERM DEFENSE.

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Policy Statement

Since Russia invaded Ukrainian territory in February 2022, a significant debate has arisen regarding Ukraine's potential inclusion in both NATO and the European Union (EU) due to the possible implications of such accessions. While distinct in nature, Ukraine's accession to the EU and NATO is central to evaluating whether its membership would enhance the defense capabilities of existing members or if it might instead represent an increased risk of conflict escalation and, consequently, war. At stake are the constraints posed by prior agreements between Ukraine and Russia, as well as international mediation efforts, which have failed to curb Russia's ambitions regarding Ukraine's territorial claims. Russia's campaign is premised on the assertion that Ukraine's ties with the West have heightened perceived threats to Russia over the years.

This political configuration is primarily characterized by the distance between Eastern European countries that were once satellites and their ongoing pursuit of political and economic autonomy. Conversely, integrating these countries into the European regime or NATO as a military alliance would represent a significant obligation for the member nations of these organizations, directly linking them to the responsibility of defending Ukraine. Consequently, the decision to broaden the scope of this responsibility, which would create an immediate reaction connection that member countries are ill-prepared for—whether due to resistance to such linkage or the capacities required—carries considerable weight.

Background

A relevant example is that of the Baltic countries, which joined NATO and the EU after years of structural reforms. Although they faced similar pressures related to their proximity to Russia, these countries benefited from the advantage of not being at war during their integration. This contrasts with the situation in Ukraine, where membership is being discussed amidst active conflict, which adds to logistical and diplomatic challenges.

Alternatively, managing support for Ukraine is a middle ground solution that favors containing associated risks while avoiding direct involvement in the war.

This support has room to expand and evolve without being characterized by decisions that imply total and unrestricted commitments. In this context, what may appear to be a hesitation in support could represent a more relevant long-term strategy for membership than the political decision to join NATO or the EU.

Models of indirect support have been observed in conflicts like Syria, where the external powers' supply of weapons and intelligence was initially intended to limit direct involvement. However, as these powers' strategic interests were impacted, support evolved into more concrete actions, such as air operations and the deployment of special forces. In the case of Ukraine, indirect support, including the transfer of weapons and military training, can create conditions for eventual more direct engagement, depending on the escalation or perceived threat by Western allies.

Asymmetric conflicts, such as the one in Ukraine, often challenge national sovereignty through territorial occupations and due to the political and economic alignment demands from allies. In this context, Ukraine must balance its decision-making autonomy with the need to integrate Western norms and standards, a process that, while essential, can be viewed internally as a restriction on sovereignty.

Logistics interoperability is among the most crucial tools for ensuring ongoing support to countries in conflict without necessitating a formal commitment to join military alliances. In Ukraine, this capability facilitates the efficient flow of equipment, resources, and information between allies, ensuring the nation's armed forces can align with Western standards. Such an approach bolsters Ukraine's military resilience and prepares the country for future integration into NATO or the EU, while reducing the risks of immediate political commitments. Sendak and Timchenko (2025) emphasize the significance of interoperability with NATO as a vital means to strengthen Ukrainian defense as the country pursues formal membership in the alliance [i].

A significant example of logistical interoperability occurred during the Afghan War, when NATO collaborated with local and international forces. Sharing supplies and standardized technology enabled highly effective joint operations, including rapidly transporting ammunition and medical equipment. However, limitations have emerged due to reliance on often inadequate local logistics systems and the lack of standardization in the weaponry used by Afghan forces, complicating the maintenance and replacement of parts. This situation underscores both the benefits and challenges of implementing logistics interoperability in prolonged conflicts.

To analyze Ukraine's membership in a collective defense system (NATO, Washington Treaty) or mutual defense (EU – Common Security and Defense Policy - CSDP), it is essential to understand the various layers associated with related capabilities and interfaces shaped by interoperability systems. These layers may contain crucial functioning mechanisms that bolster a system of mutual trust based on shared logistics, economic programs, defense, or maritime order.

In this context, NATO Codification (AC/135) serves as a vital system for standardizing logistics in defense matters. It facilitates the uniformity of product life cycles under unique and convergent criteria, impacting maintenance, purchasing, and sales systems among accredited agents. Therefore, before mobilizing resources for defense operations, the logistics system must be qualified within the supply chains to ensure its sustainability during war, along with the doctrines and mechanisms that activate the intricate network of agents and available resources [ii].

Such a complex apparatus involves participants in various roles, including states and private agents. Consequently, a network among participating states with different statuses and public and private agents ensures the adherence to production parameters in a chain that ultimately benefits the defense system. This system is already operational and has made significant progress that needs to be solidified. This is because it is within these structures, particularly the civil-military relationship, that long-term commitments are established, involving the efforts of the Defense Industrial Base and the predictability of purchases by the states.

The involvement of private companies in the production of defense systems, such as drones and artificial intelligence, has been shaping not only countries' military capabilities but also their foreign policies. Companies like Baykar, which produces Bayraktar drones, have played a central role in modern conflicts, including the situation in Ukraine, where their products are essential for military operations. This influence often extends beyond the realm of defense, creating pressure for political decisions that favor the commercial interests of these private entities, such as the approval of contracts or modifications to international regulations.

Since February 24, 2022, when Russia invaded eastern Ukraine, logistical support from the West has been systematic and essential. Since then, a war of attrition has continued without Ukraine officially declaring war on Russia, and there is little international confidence that the previous borders will be restored.

If this destabilization began years earlier with various Russian incursions in the same region, a related development occurred due to the logistical alignment in defense matters between NATO members and Ukraine. This may have contributed to Ukraine's resilience and ability to respond since February 24.

Decades earlier, the Partnership for Peace (1994) represented a significant commitment to territorial integrity and the peaceful resolution of disputes through objectives wherein relations between NATO and other actors would be guided by the promotion of transparency in national defense planning and budgeting, democratic control over armed forces, and the encouragement of participation in international peacekeeping missions and humanitarian operations under the auspices of the UN (United Nations) or the OSCE (Organization for Security and Co-operation in Europe).

Above all, the partnership sought to strengthen military cooperation through planning, exercises, and the integrated performance of military forces in joint operations, as well as the exchange of information on defense planning and budgeting. To this end, states like Ukraine would detail their participation model based on their funding. NATO is also committed to planning and assessing joint capabilities with participating states, even consulting them if they see threats to their territorial integrity, security, or political independence.

In 1997 the "Charter on a Distinct Partnership" was established, outlining NATO's cooperation with Ukraine. The Charter emphasizes interoperability and includes consultations and joint activities in conflict prevention, disarmament, counterterrorism, defense planning, and economic and political reforms. In 2002, the parties created an Action Plan, expanding their commitments to include goals such as protecting classified information and aligning national legislation with NATO standards.

The NATO-Ukraine Commission periodically assesses the implementation of these targets, tracks progress, and suggests necessary adjustments. The 2009 Supplementary Declaration, signed in Brussels, expanded this function, reinforcing the Commission's central role as a platform for overseeing and coordinating annual national programs focused on operationalizing the reforms required to fulfill Ukrainian aspirations under the decisions of the North Atlantic Council.

The declaration also allows for the extraordinary convening of the NUC in cases of threats to Ukraine's territorial integrity, political independence, or security.

The participation of the Ukrainian armed forces in joint operations under the NATO umbrella has been ongoing since 2006 in Iraq, and the Ukrainian parliament has authorized NATO troop operations on its territory since 2004 - specifically between the first Ukraine-NATO Action Plan and the Complementary Declaration.

Russia's annexation of Crimea in 2014 marked a turning point in the NATO-Ukraine relationship, leading the Alliance to reinforce its commitment to Ukrainian sovereignty and territorial integrity. Statements from the NATO-Ukraine Commission 2014 broadened the focus to include more direct responses to Russian aggression, supporting the enhancement of Ukraine's defensive capabilities and imposing economic sanctions on Russia. Furthermore, establishing mechanisms like the Trust Fund demonstrated NATO's willingness to aid defense reforms and military modernization. This resulted in a significant increase in military, humanitarian, and technical support to Ukraine, which was consolidated and renamed the Ukraine CAP Trust Fund. In addition to this fund, which was deepened following NATO's Madrid Summit (2022), the NATO-Ukraine Joint Analysis, Training and Education Centre was launched, and the NATO-Ukraine Commission was transformed into a Council, starting at the Vilnius Summit (2023) and reinforced at the Washington Summit (2024) [iii].

Findings

To strengthen the partnership, Ukraine participates in NATO's coding system, the NATO Master Catalogue for References of Logistics, which Russia was part of until its expulsion. This NATO Catalogue is managed by the NATO Support and Procurement Agency (NSPA), which supports the NATO Codification System. As a TIER 2 participant in the catalog system, Ukraine is among the countries eligible to buy and sell, including Australia, Austria, India, Brazil, Colombia, Argentina, and Morocco [iv]. The trust system is utilized in the long term through a defense economy model that coordinates product and innovation life cycles characterized by complementarity. This complementarity is the foundation for optimal interoperability, as resources are recognized and standardized across all components, ranging from civilian applications (multipurpose, subsystems, or dual-use means) to military use [v].

A practical example is standardized communication systems, such as interoperable radios and logistics management systems, which enable real-time coordination between NATO and Ukrainian units. During the ongoing conflict, anti-aircraft missiles supplied by various NATO countries were swiftly integrated into Ukrainian systems due

to the standardization of the NATO Codification System. This standardization facilitated parts replacement and efficient maintenance, even amid wartime conditions.

During the current conflict with Russia, the interoperability guaranteed by the NCS has been crucial for integrating air defense systems, such as the Patriot and NASAMS missiles, supplied by different NATO countries. Thanks to standardization, spare parts, ammunition, and technical support could be quickly shared among allies, allowing Ukrainian forces to operate these systems effectively. This increased the country's responsiveness and demonstrated how the NCS is a strategic tool for logistics coordination in highly complex scenarios.

Ukraine has invested in modernizing its defense industrial base, particularly in producing armaments and armored vehicles. A notable example is the collaboration between Ukrainian companies and European manufacturers for adapting T-72 tanks to NATO standards, including integrating compatible electronic systems. Furthermore, Ukraine has commenced producing standardized munitions under the NCS, enabling its arsenals to be quickly replenished by allied countries, thereby strengthening both interoperability and logistical resilience.

While agreed upon at the last NATO summits, the United States government is primarily responsible for determining the extent of Ukraine's defense effort. This is due not only to the available capabilities but also to the pressures on NATO's contribution structure, which presents the most sensitive aspect of the situation.

Joe Biden's administration secured a final shipment of resources to support Ukraine, including air defense missiles, air-to-ground munitions, F-16 assistance, and various small arms and ammunition types. This will enhance Ukraine's capacity to negotiate solutions to end the war by 2025. This deadline aligns more closely with his successor, Donald Trump, who shifted the expectation from 24 hours to 6 months for the war in Ukraine to conclude.

Government changes in the United States frequently redefine the focus and intensity of its involvement in international conflicts. The Biden administration, aligned with a multilateral vision, has worked to consolidate alliances and maintain support for Ukraine as a strategic pillar to contain Russia. However, if Donald Trump were to return to the presidency, that support could drastically diminish, given his history of

prioritizing domestic interests and demanding greater financial accountability from allies. This shift could destabilize Ukraine's logistical and military support balance, placing more significant pressure on European countries to address this gap.

In this scenario, Donald Trump's assumption from 2025 disrupts predictability due to certain conditions. The first condition is Trump's series of public statements at the beginning of his term regarding the potential expansion of his national security focus to the borders of Canada, Greenland, and Panama, which impacts relevant partners in his trust system. The second is linked to the expectation of investments that he imposes on his group of partners in NATO, amounting to about 5% of each nation's GDP, more than double what was previously anticipated. This increase, when realized, was not guaranteed to be sustainable among members of the Alliance.

Recommendations

While uncertainties loom over Donald Trump's role in supporting Ukraine due to the potential political and financial resistance from partners, one undeniable condition for any negotiation is Ukraine's definitive entry into the NATO system, a proposal by Volodymyr Zelenskyy. However, the same set of agreements referenced here, which predated the invasion of Ukraine, was established in layers that operated partly on general democratic principles, with conditions related to transparency, civil control, human rights, and democracy, as well as others centered on interoperability, ensured by a fundamental set of logistical measures.

The growing pressure for increased defense spending placed on NATO members directly impacts their domestic economies and social priorities. Countries like Germany and France, which maintain substantial budgets, still engage in internal debates about cuts in health, education, and infrastructure to fund enhanced military spending. In smaller economies, such as Romania and Bulgaria, this requirement can create significant social tensions, making it challenging to meet NATO spending targets and increasing the disparity between countries within the bloc. Given the elements mentioned above:

- Ukraine must deepen its integration into NATO's logistical and codification systems to improve operational efficiency and guarantee long-term sustainment.

- Aligning Ukraine's arms production with NATO standards is crucial for promoting self-sufficiency and integrating into allied supply chains.
- Securing sustainable military and financial support from NATO and EU partners, while adapting to changes in U.S. policy, is essential for Ukraine's strategic and political stability.
- Investing in cybersecurity, artificial intelligence, and advanced military systems will enhance Ukraine's resilience and long-term strategic independence.

Final Considerations

NATO's commitment to Ukraine in terms of interoperability is marked by a system that requires both doctrinal improvement and adaptation and expertise in capability systems that require sustainability in asset maintenance. Although war efforts require Ukraine to constantly adapt in the operational maintenance of its resources, many of which still belong to the Soviet system, guaranteeing the transition of its systems is the basis of its ability to safeguard its integrity.

Ukraine's complete integration into NATO relies on its military capabilities and institutional reforms that foster greater transparency and democratic oversight in defense operations. Furthermore, adherence to NATO principles necessitates Ukraine enhancing civilian oversight of its armed forces, which is crucial for maintaining the trust of other Alliance members.

However, the sustainability of Ukraine's defense lies in the standardization of systems and equipment, driven by the NATO Codification System (NCS). This allows Ukraine to receive supplies and repairs quickly, and adopting NATO standards creates opportunities for the local Ukrainian defense industry. The industry can integrate into global supply chains and become a competitive exporter of military technology adapted to international standards.

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